

A DYNAMICAL THEORY OF THE ELECTROMAGNETIC POTENTIAL

(VERSION 5)

JAMES CONOR O'BRIEN

ORCID iD 0009-0000-8895-2345

DOI 10.5281/zenodo.11511908

Keywords: Wheeler-Feynman Time-Symmetric Theory, Scalar Longitudinal Fermions, Electromagnetism, Quantum Electrodynamics, Reduced Compton Wavelength, Maxwell's Electromagnetic Model of Light, Electron Electromagnetic Model.

Abstract: This paper details a method for modelling the electron as a longitudinal electromagnetic wave in a similar method to Maxwell's equations modelling light as a transverse electromagnetic wave, gives an exact solution for the Reduced Compton Wavelength. An extension of the Wheeler-Feynman Time-symmetric theory modelling charged, massive, spinning shell particles as electromagnetic waves in a method similar to James Clerk Maxwell modelling light as electromagnetic waves, where the electron is shown to be both a charged, spinning, perfectly spherical shell in \mathbb{R}^3 and a quantized four-dimensional electromagnetic wavefunction in $\mathbb{R}^{1,3}$. Yielding for the classical Electron Charge, Mass, Velocity, Wavelength, Radius, and consistent with quantum mechanics the derived particle is shown to be necessarily On-Mass Shell and Non Self-Interacting. It is also shown Spin is a double rotation of 720° of a charged particle in the form of a spherical shell in \mathbb{R}^3 space and a single rotation of 360° of a four-dimensional scalar potential in $\mathbb{R}^{1,3}$. The result is a method to write an electromagnetic wave equation for a charged particle like an electron from the Wheeler-Feynman time-symmetric theory and Maxwell's equations for electromagnetism in the same way as Maxwell was

able to do so for the electromagnetic theory of Light.

§1 W.F.E.M.F.V.P.T.S.T.

In 1945 John Archibald Wheeler and Richard Feynman proposed the Wheeler-Feynman time-symmetric theory (W.F.T.S.T.)¹, where if \mathbf{E}_{total} is the summation of all the fields from past and future, it is taken as half because the fields are projected backwards and forwards in time so only half is needed in the summation

$$\mathbf{E}_{total} = \sum_n \frac{1}{2} (\mathbf{E}_n^{ret} + \mathbf{E}_n^{adv}) \quad (1)$$

The free fields \mathbf{E}_{free} , where the free advanced and retarded fields are those fields which interact with all the other fields in the universe besides the fields for the \mathbf{E}_{total} which is zero,

$$\mathbf{E}_{free} = \sum_n \frac{1}{2} (\mathbf{E}_n^{ret} - \mathbf{E}_n^{adv}) = 0 \quad (2)$$

Wheeler and Feynman then added the total and the free fields together

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{E}_{total} + \mathbf{E}_{free} &= \sum_n \frac{1}{2} (\mathbf{E}_n^{ret} + \mathbf{E}_n^{adv}) + \sum_n \frac{1}{2} (\mathbf{E}_n^{ret} - \mathbf{E}_n^{adv}) \\ &= \sum_n \mathbf{E}_n^{ret} \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

or

¹ Also known as the Wheeler-Feynman absorber theory.

$$\mathbf{E}_{total} = \mathbf{E}_{total} + \mathbf{E}_{free} = \mathbf{E}_{ret} \quad (4)$$

In the process the advanced fields are cancelled out, leaving only the retarded fields.

If we now rewrite the Wheeler-Feynman summation purely in terms of the four-vector potentials A_μ in Gaussian units

$$A_\mu = (\varphi/c, \mathbf{A}) \quad (5)$$

This allows to write the total Wheeler-Feynman summation as

$$A_\mu^{total} = \sum_n \frac{1}{2} (A_{\mu,n}^{ret} + A_{\mu,n}^{adv}) \quad (6)$$

the contribution of the free advanced and retarded potentials becomes,

$$A_\mu^{free} = \sum_n \frac{1}{2} (A_{\mu,n}^{ret} - A_{\mu,n}^{adv}) = 0 \quad (7)$$

leading to

$$\begin{aligned} A_\mu^{free} + A_\mu^{total} &= \sum_n \frac{1}{2} (A_{\mu,n}^{ret} - A_{\mu,n}^{adv}) + \sum_n \frac{1}{2} (A_{\mu,n}^{ret} + A_{\mu,n}^{adv}) \\ &= \sum_n A_{\mu,n}^{ret} \end{aligned} \quad (8)$$

on dropping the n index and only considering one particle we are again presented with the total potential consisting entirely of the retarded potential.

$$A_{\mu}^{\text{total}} = A_{\mu}^{\text{free}} + A_{\mu}^{\text{total}} = A_{\mu}^{\text{ret}} \quad (9)$$

This method will be labelled as the Wheeler-Feynman Electromagnetic Four-Vector Potential Time-Symmetric Theory or W.F.E.M.F.V.P.T.S.T..

Note: In the following discussion the *int* refers to intrinsic or interior, *ext* is the exterior advanced and retarded potentials.

Now consider that under the Lorenz gauge that the components of A_{μ} the $\varphi(t, \mathbf{x})$ and $\mathbf{A}(t, \mathbf{x})$ are *functionally dependent* on each other through the Lorenz gauge condition,

$$\nabla \cdot \mathbf{A} = -\frac{1}{c} \frac{\partial \varphi}{\partial t} \quad (10)$$

while under the Coulomb gauge the scalar $\varphi(t, \mathbf{x})$ and vector $\mathbf{A}(t, \mathbf{x})$ potentials become *functionally independent* of each other through (12) as it yields $\nabla \cdot \mathbf{A} = 0$ in the static frame; and as a consequence while the scalar potential is effectively instantaneous over the axis of time the vector potential is not, or quoting Griffiths:

“There is a very peculiar thing about the scalar potential in Coulomb gauge: it is determined by the distribution of charge right now. If I move an electron in my laboratory, the potential V on the moon immediately records this change. That sounds particularly odd in the light of special relativity, which allows no message to travel faster than c . The point is that V by itself is not a physically measurable quantity – all the man in the Moon can measure is \mathbf{E} , and that involves \mathbf{A} as well. Somehow it is built into the vector potential (in the Coulomb gauge) that whereas V instantaneously reflects all changes in ρ , the combination $-\nabla V - (\partial \mathbf{A} / \partial t)$ does not; \mathbf{E} will change only after sufficient time has elapsed for the “news” to arrive.” - [D. Griffiths, 2017, p441]

Therefore in order to satisfy Maxwell's equations in the relative external frames we need to introduce a new magnetic vector potential \mathbf{A}^{int} somewhere

in the space between the sources that is functionally dependent on the external scalar potentials,

$$\nabla \cdot \mathbf{A}^{int} = -\frac{1}{c} \frac{\partial \varphi_{ext}}{\partial t} \quad (11)$$

The W.F.E.M.F.V.P.T.S.T. can now be written purely in terms of the scalar potential components of the electromagnetic four potential, (although importantly the \mathbf{A} will be added later in accordance with Maxwell's equations),

$$\begin{aligned} \varphi_{total} + \varphi_{free} &= \sum_n \frac{1}{2} (\varphi_{ret} + \varphi_{adv}) + \sum_n \frac{1}{2} (\varphi_{ret} - \varphi_{adv}) \\ &= \sum_n \varphi_{ret} \end{aligned} \quad (12)$$

and we immediately recover the Wheeler-Feynman summation on writing

$$\mathbf{E} = -\nabla\varphi \quad (13)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{E}^{total} + \mathbf{E}^{free} &= \sum_n \frac{1}{2} (\mathbf{E}_n^{ret} + \mathbf{E}_n^{adv}) + \sum_n \frac{1}{2} (\mathbf{E}_n^{ret} - \mathbf{E}_n^{adv}) \\ &= \sum_n \mathbf{E}_n^{ret} \end{aligned} \quad (14)$$

This may seem an unnecessary step to recover the thing we first started out with, however, the different behaviour of φ and \mathbf{A} compared to \mathbf{E} over time requires a different approach to the problem of action at a distance. In other words, the electric potential φ and the magnetic potential \mathbf{A} are fundamentally different, the φ only exists along the axis of time and changes in its states are immediate across the entire universe, while the \mathbf{A} exists only within the local

spatial dimensions and the \mathbf{A} takes time to move through space. This doesn't violate conservation of energy, for the energy is carried through the interaction of the fields \mathbf{E} and \mathbf{B} and requires the transition of light or matter to transfer energy from here to the moon.

This means we need to apply the Wheeler-Feynman summation to φ in a fundamentally different manner to \mathbf{E} .

Using potentials instead of fields does not break Wheeler and Feynman's original conjecture that the summation takes place over the $\mathbf{E}(t, \mathbf{r})$ fields as they based their model on the time retarded Liénard-Wiechert potentials, where for $t_{\text{ret}} = t - \frac{1}{c}(\mathbf{r} - \hat{\mathbf{r}})$ is the retarded time,

$$\varphi(\mathbf{r}, t) = \frac{1}{4\pi\epsilon_0} \int \frac{\rho(\hat{\mathbf{r}}, t_{\text{ret}})}{|\mathbf{r} - \hat{\mathbf{r}}|} d^3\hat{\mathbf{r}} + \varphi_0(\mathbf{r}, t) \quad (15)$$

$$\mathbf{A}(\mathbf{r}, t) = \frac{\mu_0}{4\pi} \int \frac{\mathbf{J}(\hat{\mathbf{r}}, t_{\text{ret}})}{|\mathbf{r} - \hat{\mathbf{r}}|} d^3\hat{\mathbf{r}} + \mathbf{A}_0(\mathbf{r}, t) \quad (16)$$

Returning to the W.F.E.M.F.V.P.T.S.T. we can also note that conservation of energy requires

$$|\varphi_{\text{ext}}| = |\varphi_{\text{int}}| \quad (17)$$

or

$$\left| \frac{q_{\text{ext}}}{r_{\text{ext}}} \right| = \left| \frac{q_{\text{int}}}{r_{\text{int}}} \right| \quad (18)$$

To write this as an electromagnetic wave for a massive particle requires

the charge on the particle be the same as for the advanced and retarded particles, therefore

$$q_{int} = q_{ext} = q \quad (19)$$

and the radius of the particles

$$r_{ext} = r_{int} \quad (20)$$

Having $r_{ext} = r_{int}$ means *the intrinsic potential appears exactly midway between the original potentials.*

We can also note the radius r must be greater than zero to avoid infinite energy then radius r can be derived from

$$\mathbf{E}_{int} = -\nabla \frac{q_{int}}{r_{int}} \quad (21)$$

Having this we can also note the mass-energy relationship requires there must be a mass associated with the energy of the charge which must equal the rest mass of the particle.

In other words, not only is the point where the intrinsic potential appears exactly midway between the original potentials but also the resultant intrinsic charge is the same as the original charges, this simplifies the potential to

$$\begin{aligned}
\varphi_{\text{total}} &= \sum_n \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{q}{r_{\text{ret}}} + \frac{q}{r_{\text{adv}}} \right) + \sum_n \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{q}{r_{\text{ret}}} - \frac{q}{r_{\text{adv}}} \right) \\
&= \frac{q}{r_{\text{ret}}} \\
&\equiv \frac{q}{r_{\text{int}}}
\end{aligned} \tag{22}$$

Maxwell's equations must now be applied to the intrinsic frame to prevent the system from being unbalanced (*this is the decisive step*), to do so first take the Coulomb gauge in the extrinsic frames, we can do this because as was pointed out above the \mathbf{A}_{ext} vanishes in the intrinsic frame,

$$\nabla \cdot \mathbf{A}_{\text{ext}} = 0 \tag{23}$$

In other words, the magnetic potentials from the relative future and past frames do not extend to the local frame of reference. However, since Maxwell's equations are Lorentz invariant we must satisfy them by switching to the Lorenz gauge in the new frame, and in the intrinsic frame *a new magnetic potential* (\mathbf{A}_{int}) appears as due to the *time varying extrinsic electric potentials*, or

$$\nabla \cdot \mathbf{A}_{\text{int}} = -\frac{1}{c} \sum_n \partial \varphi_{\text{ext},n} / \partial t \tag{24}$$

now summing over all the extrinsic potentials φ_{ret} , φ_{adv}

$$\nabla \cdot \mathbf{A}_{\text{int}} = -\frac{1}{c} \sum_n \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{\partial \varphi_{\text{ret}}}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial \varphi_{\text{adv}}}{\partial t} \right) - \frac{1}{c} \sum_n \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{\partial \varphi_{\text{ret}}}{\partial t} - \frac{\partial \varphi_{\text{adv}}}{\partial t} \right) \tag{25}$$

We can then solve for \mathbf{A}^{int} using Gauss's theorem to integrate over a volume resulting in the magnetic vector potential radiating from the surface of the volume

$$\mathbf{A}^{int} \cdot \hat{n} = -\frac{1}{c} \frac{\partial \phi}{\partial t} \quad (26)$$

under Helmholtz's theorem a new \mathbf{B}^{int} also appears,

$$\mathbf{B}_{int} = \nabla \times \mathbf{A}_{int} \quad (27)$$

as well as the intrinsic electric field in the local frame,

$$\mathbf{E}_{int} = -\nabla \varphi_{int} - \frac{1}{c} \partial \mathbf{A}_{int} / \partial t \quad (28)$$

We have now recovered the original summation for the W.F.E.M.F.V.P.T.S.T. by writing

$$A_{\mu}^{int} = (\varphi_{int}/c, \mathbf{A}_{int}) \quad (29)$$

$$\begin{aligned} A_{\mu}^{tot} &= \frac{1}{2} \Sigma (A_{\mu}^{ret} - A_{\mu}^{adv}) + \frac{1}{2} \Sigma (A_{\mu}^{ret} + A_{\mu}^{adv}) \\ &= A_{\mu}^{ret} \\ &\equiv A_{\mu}^{int} \end{aligned} \quad (30)$$

However, there is one extra detail that needs to be considered, the intrinsic electrical field \mathbf{E}_{int} appears along the axis of time from the electric potential

$$\mathbf{E}_{int} = -\nabla \varphi_{ext} \quad (31)$$

while the intrinsic magnetic field \mathbf{B}_{int} appears from the cross product

$$\mathbf{B}_{\text{int}} = \nabla \times \mathbf{A}_{\text{int}} \quad (32)$$

which in turn appears from

$$\nabla \cdot \mathbf{A}_{\text{int}} = -\frac{1}{c} \sum_n \frac{\partial \varphi_{\text{ext},n}}{\partial t} \quad (33)$$

In other words, the Poynting vector of the cross product of the \mathbf{E}_{int} and \mathbf{B}_{int} fields appears as *a current across the surface* of the intersection where

$$\hat{\mathbf{S}} = \frac{1}{\mu_0} (\mathbf{E}_{\text{int}} \times \mathbf{B}_{\text{int}}) \quad (34)$$

In the section on electromagnetic spin (§3) this current will be shown to be travelling at the speed of light.

We can also see the W.F.T.S.T. as a subspace of the W.F.E.M.F.V.P.T.S.T., as there appears within the context of the Wheeler-Feynman model a cycle of electromagnetic potentials over the particles evolution,

$$A_{\mu}^{\text{ret,adv}} \rightarrow \varphi^{\text{ext}} \rightarrow \mathbf{A}^{\text{int}} \rightarrow \varphi^{\text{int}} \rightarrow (\mathbf{B}^{\text{int}}, \mathbf{E}^{\text{int}}) \rightarrow A_{\mu}^{\text{int}} \quad (35)$$

So what does this all mean? Imagine two separated electrons in the advanced and retarded frames of reference moving along the time axis. At any

moment in time in their frames of reference they are in the Coulomb gauge in the \mathbb{R}^3 space, and $\varphi(t, \mathbf{r}) > 0$ and the $\nabla \cdot \mathbf{A}(t, \mathbf{r}) = 0$, meaning and effectively there is no \mathbf{A} in \mathbb{R}^3 . However, from the relative frame of reference of a point midway between these two sources - the electrons are either moving towards or away from. In which case, we expect both $\varphi(t, \mathbf{r}) > 0$ and $\nabla \cdot \mathbf{A}(t, \mathbf{r}) > 0$, for this to happen we must apply the Lorenz gauge $\nabla \cdot \mathbf{A} = -\frac{1}{c} \frac{\partial \varphi}{\partial t}$ in $\mathbb{R}^{1,3}$, which after integrating over the volume of a sphere leads directly to

$$\mathbf{A} \cdot \hat{n} = -\frac{1}{c} \frac{\partial \phi}{\partial t} \tag{36}$$

This is the crucial idea in this model, by switching from the Coulomb gauge in the \mathbb{R}^3 to Lorenz gauge in $\mathbb{R}^{1,3}$ requires the appearance of a new electron midway between the two original electrons.

So similar to Maxwell's derivation for light where time and spatial dependent fields \mathbf{E} and \mathbf{B} generate each other through time varying fields, in this paper the time and spatially dependent potentials φ and \mathbf{A} also generate each other in a cyclic manner through time varying potentials. Thus the W.F.E.M.F.V.P.T.S.T. gives us the beginning of what might be an electromagnetic wave equation for a charged fundamental particle, so let's now try to quantize this and derive a quantum mechanical model for this W.F.E.M.F.V.P.T.S.T..

§2 Electromagnetic Wave Function

What we really want is a wave function equation for the electromagnetic

matter wave that is based on the action S

$$S = \int \mathcal{L}(\dot{x}, x)dt = \int T - Vdt \quad (37)$$

noting S is governed by Hamilton's Principle for Least Action, and for generalised coordinates $\eta(t)$

$$\frac{\delta S_{total}}{\delta \eta(t)} = 0 \quad (38)$$

allows us to write Hamilton's principle in terms of the advanced and retarded actions

$$\frac{\delta S_{total}}{\delta \eta(t)} = \sum \left(\frac{\delta S_{ret}}{\delta \eta(t)} + \frac{\delta S_{adv}}{\delta \eta(t)} \right) = 0 \quad (39)$$

Since we are trying to model an electromagnetic wave as a plane wave we can assume the difference between the two actions is zero

$$\Delta S = S_{ret} - S_{adv} = 0 \quad (40)$$

Since $S = Et$, or the units of Energy times Time, we can rewrite the actions in terms of energies at time t

$$\Delta Et = E_{ret}t - E_{adv}t = 0 \quad (41)$$

If t is a constant, or strictly we are choosing a single moment in the evolution of the system, then we can remove the time factor and see the difference in energy is also zero

$$\Delta E = E_{ret} - E_{adv} = 0 \quad (42)$$

This is important because it means conservation of energy is preserved and therefore the difference in frequency $\Delta\omega$ is also zero, now we can quantize the energy as necessary for a quantum mechanical wave equation,

$$\Delta\omega = \frac{\Delta E}{\hbar} = \frac{E_{ret} - E_{adv}}{\hbar} = 0 \quad (43)$$

If the phase is given by

$$\theta = \int \Delta\omega(t)dt = 0 \quad (44)$$

then the phase difference $\Delta\theta$ is given by

$$\Delta\theta = \theta_1 - \theta_2 = 0 \quad (45)$$

From this it follows that S_1 and S_2 must be in phase, in other words, we can add ΔS to the total action:

If and only if the Advanced and Retarded Potentials are in Phase

This is important because it means the past and future of these particles are in phase, if they were out of phase then they would constructively or destructively interfere with each other, so from now on we will refer to ΔS as the *action interference term*.

From Hamilton's principle (equation 39) we can write

$$\frac{\delta S_{total}}{\delta \eta(t)} = \frac{\delta S_{adv}}{\delta \eta(t)} = \frac{\delta S_{ret}}{\delta \eta(t)} = -\frac{\delta S_{adv}}{\delta \eta(t)} = 0 \quad (46)$$

Now we can write

$$\frac{\delta S_{total}}{\delta \eta(t)} = \sum \left(\frac{\delta S_{ret}}{\delta \eta(t)} + \frac{\delta S_{adv}}{\delta \eta(t)} + \frac{\delta S_{ret}}{\delta \eta(t)} - \frac{\delta S_{adv}}{\delta \eta(t)} \right) = 0 \quad (47)$$

since all of this equals zero we can without loss of that generality rewrite this with factors² of a $\frac{1}{2}$

$$\frac{\delta S_{total}}{\delta \eta(t)} = \sum \left(\frac{1}{2} \frac{\delta S_{ret}}{\delta \eta(t)} + \frac{1}{2} \frac{\delta S_{adv}}{\delta \eta(t)} + \frac{1}{2} \frac{\delta S_{ret}}{\delta \eta(t)} - \frac{1}{2} \frac{\delta S_{adv}}{\delta \eta(t)} \right) = 0 \quad (48)$$

We can now drop the principle of least action and extract the intrinsic total action, and in the process reproducing the Wheeler-Feynman time-symmetric summation using only the action terms.

$$\begin{aligned} S_{tot} &= \frac{1}{2} \sum (S_{ret} + S_{adv} + S_{ret} - S_{adv}) \\ &= S_{ret} \\ &\equiv S_{int} \end{aligned} \quad (49)$$

What we want, however, is a wave function formulation, and we can do this immediately, we only need to express the action in four-vector notation by making the following substitution,

² The factor of $\frac{1}{2}$ can be interpreted as only half of a potential pointing forwards or backwards in time so only half the advanced or retarded potential can interact with its opposite.

$$S = \frac{iq}{\hbar} A_\mu \quad (50)$$

in doing so we are also switching from the action formulation to the quantum field formulation, now we have

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{iq}{\hbar} A_\mu^{\text{tot}} &= \frac{iq}{2\hbar} \sum (A_\mu^{\text{ret}} + A_\mu^{\text{adv}}) + (A_\mu^{\text{ret}} - A_\mu^{\text{adv}}) \\ &= \frac{iq}{\hbar} A_\mu^{\text{ret}} \\ &\equiv \frac{iq}{\hbar} A_\mu^{\text{int}} \end{aligned} \quad (51)$$

You will note our wave functions are either half or full wave functions, so I'm going to use the lower case ψ for half wave functions and the upper case Ψ for full wave functions, the 'half' refers to either the extrinsic advanced or retarded A_μ .

$$\psi = \exp\left[-\frac{iq}{2\hbar} \int A_\mu dx^\mu\right] \quad (52)$$

I want to now re-express this explicitly as a wave function model in terms of the Wheeler-Feynman time-symmetric theory by including the initial phases as epoch angles ε of both the advanced and retarded half wave functions, these epoch angles are taken from the zero of the action interference term

$$\psi_{\text{ret}} = \exp\left[-\frac{iq}{2\hbar} \int A_\mu^{\text{ret}} dx^\mu + \varepsilon_{\text{ret}}\right] \quad (53)$$

$$\psi_{\text{adv}} = \exp\left[-\frac{iq}{2\hbar} \int A_\mu^{\text{adv}} dx^\mu + \varepsilon_{\text{adv}}\right] \quad (54)$$

The epoch angles now take the place of Wheeler-Feynman's original free terms, allowing us to write

$$\psi_{\text{ret}} \cdot \psi_{\text{adv}} = \exp\left[-\frac{iq}{2\hbar} \int A_{\mu}^{\text{ret}} dx^{\mu} + \varepsilon_{\text{ret}} - \frac{iq}{2\hbar} \int A_{\mu}^{\text{adv}} dx^{\mu} + \varepsilon_{\text{adv}}\right] \quad (55)$$

and on equating the epoch angles to ensure a constant phase

$$\varepsilon_{\text{adv}} + \varepsilon_{\text{ret}} = 0 \quad (56)$$

i.e.,

$$\varepsilon_{\text{ret}} = -\varepsilon_{\text{adv}} \quad (57)$$

We can without loss of generality substitute the epoch angles with the retarded and advanced potentials of the free terms

$$\varepsilon_{\text{ret}} = -\frac{iq}{2\hbar} \int A_{\mu}^{\text{ret}} dx^{\mu} \quad (58)$$

$$\varepsilon_{\text{adv}} = \frac{iq}{2\hbar} \int A_{\mu}^{\text{adv}} dx^{\mu} \quad (59)$$

We can write this if and only if the phase difference between the advanced and retarded potentials is zero, which is perfectly acceptable because we would expect the different parts of an electromagnetic wave to be in phase with themselves, so now writing in full

$$\Psi_{\text{total}} = \exp\left[\frac{iq}{2\hbar} \left(-\int A_{\mu}^{\text{ret}} dx^{\mu} - \int A_{\mu}^{\text{ret}} dx^{\mu} - \int A_{\mu}^{\text{adv}} dx^{\mu} + \int A_{\mu}^{\text{adv}} dx^{\mu} \right)\right] \quad (60)$$

Once again the advanced terms cancel out, the half wave functions add to a full wave function, and we are left with the intrinsic four-vector potential form of the wave function

$$\begin{aligned} \Psi_{\text{total}} &= \exp\left[-\frac{iq}{\hbar} \int A_{\mu}^{\text{int}} dx^{\mu}\right] \\ &= \Psi_{\text{int}} \\ &\equiv \Psi_{\text{ret}} \end{aligned} \quad (61)$$

We see this completely expresses the Wheeler-Feynman model in wave function formulation for the four-vector potential A_{μ} .

The interference term has the added benefit of making the wave equation *on mass shell*, for if

$$E_{\text{ret}} - E_{\text{adv}} \neq 0 \quad (62)$$

then either

$$E_{\text{adv}}^2 \geq |\vec{p}|^2 c^2 + m_0^2 c^4 \quad \text{or} \quad E_{\text{adv}}^2 \leq |\vec{p}|^2 c^2 + m_0^2 c^4 \quad (63)$$

and the resulting wave equation would off mass shell.

Therefore if $\Delta E = 0$ the particle must be on mass shell

The resulting waveform is manifestly Lorentz invariant, where *importantly the equality of $E^2 = |\vec{p}|^2 c^2 + m_0^2 c^4$ allows us to derive Dirac's equation for a charged particle, in other words, this method leads directly to Dirac's relativistic wave equation for matter.* Not bad for simply equating the energy of the future to the past or what is commonly known as conservation of energy.

Obviously this is different from Wheeler and Feynman's original idea where the radiation of the free terms emitted by each particle is completely absorbed by all other particles present in the universe. That necessitates an interaction with the entire universe which was a serious problem with their model and often brought up in criticism, it also didn't explain the problem of self-interaction. In this model the *zero of self interaction* not only gives a mechanism for the free particles without recourse to the entire universe, it also *removes the problem of self-interaction* itself — as this model only works if the self-interaction is zero which is only possible if and only if the phase difference between the advanced and retarded potentials is zero—indeed if the interference term is non zero this model fails, and as a result it is in the language of Poincaré '*non self-interacting*'.

We can improve upon the above formulation by noting that according to the Feynman-Stueckelberg interpretation [Griffiths 2008 p.21] the positron is the negative energy mode of the electron field moving backward in time, and since the complex conjugates of the advanced and retarded wave functions take the convenient form of being conjugates of each other, we can make some

identities

$$|\psi_{\text{ret}}| = |\psi_{\text{adv}}| \quad (64)$$

$$\psi_{\text{ret}} = \psi_{\text{adv}}^* \quad (65)$$

$$\psi_{\text{adv}} = \psi_{\text{ret}}^* \quad (66)$$

$$\psi_{\text{ret}} \cdot \psi_{\text{ret}}^* = I \quad (67)$$

$$\psi_{\text{total}} = \psi_{\text{ret}} \cdot \psi_{\text{adv}} \quad (68)$$

$$\psi_{\text{interference}} = \psi_{\text{ret}} \cdot \psi_{\text{adv}}^* = I \quad (69)$$

This allows us to can write the W.F.E.M.F.V.P.T.S.T. in its most elegant form,

$$\begin{aligned} \Psi_{\text{total}} &= \psi_{\text{total}} \cdot \psi_{\text{interference}} \\ &= \psi_{\text{ret}} \cdot \psi_{\text{adv}} \cdot \psi_{\text{ret}} \cdot \psi_{\text{adv}}^* \\ &= \psi_{\text{ret}} \cdot \psi_{\text{ret}}^* \cdot \psi_{\text{ret}} \cdot \psi_{\text{ret}}^{**} \\ &= \psi_{\text{ret}} \cdot \psi_{\text{ret}}^* \cdot \psi_{\text{ret}} \cdot \psi_{\text{ret}} \quad (70) \\ &= \psi_{\text{ret}} \cdot \psi_{\text{ret}} \\ &= \Psi_{\text{ret}} \\ &\equiv \Psi_{\text{intrinsic}} \end{aligned}$$

While the model deals with the temporal component of the wave function it does not, however, consider the spatial component of the phase of the momentum, so to quantize the momentum we must consider the definition of electromagnetic momentum as

$$q\mathbf{A} = \mathbf{p} \quad (71)$$

if r is the spatial distance between the potentials leads to

$$\int q\mathbf{A}dx = \mathbf{p}r \quad (72)$$

in generalised coordinates

$$\int p_\mu dx^\mu = q \int A_\mu dx^\mu = q \int \varphi dt + q \int \mathbf{A}dx \quad (73)$$

to introduce the quantization of the wave function where the end points of the standing wave are the sources of the advanced and retarded potentials, write

$$2\pi q \int A_\mu dx^\mu = nh \quad (74)$$

or absorbing the 2π into the Planck's constant

$$q \int A_\mu dx^\mu = n\hbar \quad (75)$$

yielding the phase θ

$$\theta = \frac{q}{\hbar} \int A_\mu dx^\mu \quad (76)$$

Now we can write the spatial component in terms of the magnetic potential of the wave function as

$$\Psi_{spatial} = \exp\left[-\frac{iq}{\hbar} \int \mathbf{A}_{int} dx\right] \quad (77)$$

combining this with the temporal definition of a wave function, yields

$$\Psi_{temporal} \Psi_{spatial} = \exp\left[-\frac{iq}{\hbar} \int \varphi_{ext} dt\right] \cdot \exp\left[-\frac{iq}{\hbar} \int \mathbf{A}_{int} dx\right] \quad (78)$$

leads to the quantization of the four-vector potential wave function

$$\Psi_{total} = \Psi_{temporal} \Psi_{spatial} = -\frac{iq}{\hbar} \int A_{\mu} dx^{\mu} \quad (79)$$

In other words, we can construct a wave function entirely in agreement with Wheeler's and Feynman model only we have generalized it using the Four-Vector Potential.

§3 Electromagnetic Charge

We can now interpret this as an electromagnetic wave by writing Ampere-Maxwell's law

$$\nabla \times \mathbf{B} = \frac{4\pi}{c} \mathbf{J} + \frac{1}{c} \frac{\partial \mathbf{E}}{\partial t} \quad (80)$$

then in the intrinsic frame we can use the vector triple product

$$\begin{aligned}
\nabla \times (\nabla \times \mathbf{A}_{int}) &= \nabla (\nabla \cdot \mathbf{A}_{int}) - \nabla^2 \mathbf{A}_{int} \\
&= \frac{4\pi}{c} \mathbf{j}_{int} - \frac{1}{c} \nabla \frac{d\varphi_{int}}{dt} - \frac{1}{c} \frac{d^2 \mathbf{A}_{int}}{dt^2}
\end{aligned} \tag{81}$$

and by applying the Lorenz gauge transformation

$$A^\mu \rightarrow A^\mu + \partial^\mu f \tag{82}$$

we can derive the D'Alembertian for an electromagnetic wave

$$\square^2 \mathbf{A}_{int} = -\frac{4\pi}{c} \mathbf{j}_{int} \tag{83}$$

In other words, we have derived a time-symmetric electromagnetic wave equation that preserves energy and charge in a manner that is consistent with Maxwell's equations. The principle difference between this model and Maxwell's equations for light, is that light is a transverse electromagnetic wave while this model is an *oblique* electromagnetic wave — the \mathbf{E} and \mathbf{B} fields of light are *transverse* in space to the path of motion for light, while the φ_{ext} potential is *obliquely* to the axis of motion and the \mathbf{A}_{int} only appears in the local frame of reference — what we have done is rotate a photon 45° into the axis of time:

Effectively we have derived Maxwell's equations for the electron.

Let's examine the charge for a four-potential wave equation in greater detail, as shown above the resultant extrinsic electric potential in the particle's frame of reference is radially directed from the surface of the intermediate particle – effectively this is the Bare Charge of the electron.

(fig. 1)

We can then say that in any frame of reference there is a unique set of electrical field vectors that are radially directed from the origin of the particle and by Gauss' law this is equivalent to a source point charge q at the origin of the intermediate coordinate, and at every point in the evolution of the motion of the particle there exists a unique solution to the electromagnetic wave equation as a spherical charged shell, importantly there are no fields \mathbf{E} or \mathbf{B} within the spherical shell.

To establish the charge for this shell from the wave equation first write the four dimensional D'Alembertian for the A^μ

$$\square^2 A^\mu = -\frac{4\pi}{c} J^\mu \quad (84)$$

from this we can extract the three dimensional charge from the current

density

$$\nabla \cdot \mathbf{j} = -\frac{\partial \rho}{\partial t} \quad (85)$$

and applying Gauss' divergence theorem where the rate of change of charge in a fixed volume Ω equals the net current flowing through the boundary yields the charge

$$\frac{dq_{\Omega}}{dt} = \frac{d}{dt} \iiint_{\Omega} \rho dV = - \oiint_{\partial\Omega} \mathbf{j} \cdot d\hat{S} = -I_{\partial\Omega} \quad (86)$$

In other words, we have transformed from a four dimensional space $\mathbb{R}^{1,3}$ to a three dimensional space \mathbb{R}^3 , we have gone from a four dimensional waveform to a three dimensional sphere, and if we now integrate over this unit sphere we obtain the charge which is identified with the sphere of the intrinsic electric field. Application of Gauss's divergence theorem immediately explains how these charged spheres can appear to be point particles, this electromagnetic sphere behaves as a point charge even where there is no point charge, and in so doing this resolves two important problems in particle physics, firstly there is no infinite energy associated with a point particle as the charge is no longer condensed into a point with an infinite energy density (a major sticking point in the history of particle physics), and secondly the origin of charge, charge itself now appears as a simple expression of Maxwell's equations, indeed we can even go so far as to say that four dimensionally there is no charge only the potentials, however since we can't measure the potentials only the charges we are stuck with charge as a fundamental property of matter. It all comes down to a frame of reference, the potentials are dependent on extrinsic frames of

reference but the charges must be in the local intrinsic frame of reference, so depending on whether we are considering the abstract potentials or measuring particle charges depends on whether we are measuring the wave or the particle.

We can reasonably expect the four dimensional potentials to be perfectly spherical about the extrinsic charges, this requires the resultant charged particles are also perfectly spherical, in fact if aspherical particles are detected that would invalidate the present model. As a proof of this concept it must be pointed out that a ten year study of the shape of the electron at the Imperial's Centre for Cold Matter have demonstrated that the electron is for all practical requirements perfectly spherical, the following is a verbatim of the paper's abstract:

“The electron is predicted to be slightly aspheric, with a distortion characterized by the electric dipole moment (EDM), d_e . No experiment has ever detected this deviation. The standard model of particle physics predicts that d_e is far too small to detect, being some eleven orders of magnitude smaller than the current experimental sensitivity. However, many extensions to the standard model naturally predict much larger values of d_e that should be detectable. This makes the search for the electron EDM a powerful way to search for new physics and constrain the possible extensions. In particular, the popular idea that new supersymmetric particles may exist at masses of a few hundred GeV/c^2 (where c is the speed of light) is difficult to reconcile with the absence of an electron EDM at the present limit of sensitivity. The size of the EDM is also intimately related to the question of why the Universe has so little antimatter. If the reason is that some undiscovered particle interaction breaks the symmetry between matter and antimatter, this should result in a measurable EDM in most models of particle physics. Here we use cold polar molecules to measure the

electron EDM at the highest level of precision reported so far, providing a constraint on any possible new interactions. I which sets a new upper limit of $|de| < 10.5 \times 10^{-28} e \text{ cm}$ with 90 per cent confidence. This result, consistent with zero, indicates that the electron is spherical at this improved level of precision. Our measurement of atto-electronvolt energy shifts in a molecule probes new physics at the tera-electronvolt energy scale.” [Hudson, Kara, Smallman, Sauer, Tarbutt, Hinds 2011]

This idea of the elementary particles being perfect spheres harks back to Poincaré’s original conception of particles as being hollow charged spheres that led to his extraordinary statement in his paper “La fin de la matière” that matter no longer exists:

“One of the most surprising discoveries made by the physicists in recent years, amounts in the claim that matter doesn’t exist. We simultaneously add, that this discovery is not definitely established. The essential property of matter is its mass and its inertia. Mass remains constant everywhere and always, it even remains when a chemical transformation changes all observable properties of matter, and has apparently created an entirely new body. Thus if one is able to show, that matter carries mass like a foreign jewellery, that this mass (always considered as constant) can also suffer variations: then one surely has the right to say that there is no matter. But this is precisely what is announced.” [Poincaré 1906]

Contrary to Poincaré, I am not suggesting matter does not exist, rather I’m suggesting matter is an intermediate state of the electromagnetic four dimensional waveform, the problem lies in choosing a frame of reference. Is it a potential? Is it a wave? Is it a particle? Is it a sphere? That all depends on what mathematical framework is used to describe the motion of matter, a better

description would be that it is all contingent on where you stand in the universe.
 For now let's state as a provisional rule:

The intrinsic charge of the particle in \mathbb{R}^3 is derived under the Lorenz gauge from the sum of the extrinsic retarded and advanced potentials in $\mathbb{R}^{1,3}$.

We can also express the wavelength and frequency of the resultant particles in terms of the above energy-momentum vector space using the de Broglie relations

$$\frac{h}{p} = \lambda \tag{87}$$

$$E = \frac{h}{\omega} \tag{88}$$

equating Planck's constant result in

$$E\omega = \lambda p \tag{89}$$

the ratio of the energy-momentum vector space now becomes

$$\frac{E}{p} = \frac{\lambda}{\omega} \tag{90}$$

if we use φ_{int} as the summation of the advanced and retarded potentials of the Wheeler-Feynman summation, and the derived \mathbf{A}_{int} we can show

$$\frac{e}{p} = \frac{q|\varphi_{int}|}{q|\mathbf{A}_{int}|} = \frac{\lambda}{\omega} \tag{91}$$

therefore the wavelength and frequency result from the relationship between the energy and momentum

$$\frac{|\varphi|}{|\mathbf{A}|} = \frac{\lambda}{\omega} \quad (92)$$

A charged electromagnetic wave, however, requires a current

$$\frac{1}{\mu_0} \nabla \times \mathbf{B} - \epsilon_0 \frac{\partial \mathbf{E}}{\partial t} = \mathbf{J} \quad (93)$$

Thus there appears an intrinsic current density that flows along with the particle

$$\mathbf{J}_{int} = \epsilon_0 \frac{\partial^2 \phi_{int}}{\partial t^2} \quad (94)$$

From \mathbf{J}_{int} we can determine the current density

$$\nabla \cdot \mathbf{J}_{int} = -\frac{\partial \rho}{\partial t} \quad (95)$$

from $\rho = nq$ where $n = 1$ and q is the charge on the electron we can determine the drift velocity \mathbf{u}

$$\mathbf{J}_{int} = \rho \mathbf{u} \quad (96)$$

To show this velocity is equal to the velocity of the electron (or quark) we merely resort to the relativistic mass-energy relation

$$E_{rel}^2 = (pc)^2 + (m_0c^2)^2 \quad (97)$$

the rest energy is taken from the scalar potential times the charge

$$E_{rel}^2 = (pc)^2 + (q\varphi)^2 \quad (98)$$

where the \mathbf{v} in the momentum \mathbf{p} is given by

$$\mathbf{v} = \frac{\mathbf{p}}{m} \quad (99)$$

By conservation of energy the angle between the direction of motion of the particle in space-like coördinates and the \mathbf{E} and \mathbf{B} fields in time-like coördinates must be at 45° , where the \mathbf{E} and \mathbf{B} fields travel as an electromagnetic wave at the speed of light c along the axis of light (R) in $\mathbb{R}^{1,3}$ as (fig. 2)

$$c = \frac{R}{T} \quad (100)$$

but if we transform along the axis of motion (x) of the particle in \mathbb{R}^3 where

$$R = \sqrt{2}x \quad (101)$$

$$T = \sqrt{2}t \quad (102)$$

we arrive at the velocity of the particle in space-like coordinates

$$c' = \frac{R}{T} \rightarrow \frac{\sqrt{2}x}{\sqrt{2}t} = \frac{x}{t} = v \quad (103)$$

Importantly this v is the classical velocity of the charged particle.

This may seem a paradoxical result, however, since the \mathbf{E} and \mathbf{B} fields are moving along the light cone in imaginary space we can ignore that problem because again we can't measure the imaginary velocity of electromagnetic wave while we are in \mathbb{R}^3 - we can only measure the physical velocity. The important thing is that an electromagnetic wave carrying charge moves at the speed of the particle, indeed it always transforms the coordinates of light into the coordinates of matter regardless of the speed of the electromagnetic wave.

This in turn transforms our electromagnetic wave equation for the vector potential to

$$\nabla^2 \mathbf{A}' - \frac{1}{v^2} \frac{\partial^2 \mathbf{A}'}{\partial t^2} = -\mu_0 \mathbf{J}' \quad (104)$$

Which parallels Maxwell's equations for the movement of light, for by arriving at the classical velocity for an electron you can clearly see the unambiguous relation of this model to Maxwell's derivation for the speed of light for electromagnetic waves, for in the exact same manner as Maxwell showed '*light travels at c* ' we have shown '*matter travels at v* ' as a result of Maxwell's equations.

You can see that associated with this time-symmetric electromagnetic wave is a current which we observe in our three-dimensional space as a charged particle moving forward along the axis of time — in other words, it looks like an electron. So it follows that the velocity of the current is given by (99), in effect the electromagnetic wave gives the speed of the associated particle is directly related to the speed of light, i.e., the \mathbf{E} and \mathbf{B} fields moving at the speed of light c across the surface of the spherical shell in $\mathbb{R}^{1,3}$ are solved to give the speed \mathbf{v} of the charged particle in \mathbb{R}^3 . This is a spectacular and completely unexpected result, it says matter is both an electromagnetic wave in $\mathbb{R}^{1,3}$ and a classical particle in \mathbb{R}^3 . Now we can explicitly say:

*By applying Maxwell's equations to the Wheeler-Feynman summation we have derived the electromagnetic wave function for charged particles, or
Matter is a form of Light and Light is a form of Matter.*

§4 Electromagnetic Spin

We now have almost everything we need to write an electromagnetic wave equation for a massive and charged elementary particle, but quantum spin is missing and without spin this particle won't fly.

Hans Ohanian³ noted the possibility in 1986 that the spin of electron might arise from some internal electromagnetic dynamics. So let's try and achieve a spinning, charged, electromagnetic wave using Maxwell's equations and the Wheeler-Feynman summation. To satisfy Maxwell's equations in the intrinsic frame, and I'll repeat the above summation for the magnetic vector potential is in the extrinsic frames, we must do this because as pointed out

3(Ohanian H.C. (1986) What is spin? Am J Phys 54:500—505 30))

above the extrinsic magnetic potential \mathbf{A}_{ext} vanishes in the intrinsic frame,

$$\nabla \cdot \mathbf{A}_{ext} = 0 \quad (105)$$

However, since Maxwell's equations are Lorentz invariant we can satisfy them by switching to the Lorenz gauge in the new frame, therefore in the intrinsic frame a new magnetic potential appears due to the time varying extrinsic electric potentials, or

$$\nabla \cdot \mathbf{A}_{int} = -\frac{1}{c} \frac{\partial \varphi_{ext}}{\partial t} \quad (106)$$

or in the Wheeler-Feynman formulation

$$\nabla \cdot \mathbf{A}_{int} = -\frac{1}{c} \sum_n \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{\partial \varphi_{ret}}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial \varphi_{adv}}{\partial t} \right) - \frac{1}{c} \sum_n \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{\partial \varphi_{ret}}{\partial t} - \frac{\partial \varphi_{adv}}{\partial t} \right) \quad (107)$$

This says that to satisfy Maxwell's equations *a magnetic potential appears out of nowhere midway between the advanced and retarded potentials.*

If there is an intrinsic magnetic potential then there is also an intrinsic magnetic field \mathbf{B}_{int} and now something occurs that I think is truly amazing ... if we now calculate the intrinsic magnetic field from the cross product of the intrinsic potential

$$\mathbf{B}_{int} = \nabla \times \mathbf{A}_{int} \quad (108)$$

the \mathbf{B}_{int} appears as a three-dimensional field *across the surface of the sphere of the intrinsic charge*, this is only possible if the *charge is spinning in a three-dimensional space*, in other words

*SPIN itself appears in the local frame
as a natural consequence of Maxwell's equations*

Noting the four-vector potential is in $\mathbb{R}^{1,3}$ and the charged sphere is in \mathbb{R}^3 , we can also state the A_{ret}^μ and A_{adv}^μ are in a two-to-one relationship that forms a double-cover of the A_{total}^μ , and we can project the waveforms of the advanced and retarded potentials to form two four-dimensional vector potential spheres centred on the advanced and retarded charges. This resultant third four-dimensional sphere appears in the physical space \mathbb{R}^3 at the intersection of two four-dimensional hyperspheres $\mathbb{R}^{1,3}$ as the surface of a charged sphere in three-dimensional space. If we write the wavefunction in it's phase θ

$$\theta = \frac{q}{\hbar} \int A_\mu dx^\mu \tag{109}$$

The observant amongst you will note that if we rotate the vector potential sphere in $\mathbb{R}^{1,3}$ then the charged sphere in \mathbb{R}^3 rotates twice as fast, indeed if we rotate the charged sphere in \mathbb{R}^3 a complete 720° then the vector potential rotates 360° suggesting the A_μ behaves just like the Spin of a wave-function, but this shouldn't be surprising as we know the A_μ is the wave-function for a photon. This double-rotation is the hallmark of quantum spin, in effect this model behaves exactly as we would want an electron to behave.

We can visualise this as a 3D sphere covered with magnetic loops with

electric fields projecting from its surface, (fig. 3)

It is not that the electron is spinning at the speed of light, rather the electric and magnetic fields produce a wave that moves at the speed of the light only on the surface of the particle, and the time variation of the electric charge produces a magnetic field that is the equivalent of a spinning charged particle with mass given by the mass-energy equivalence

$$m = \frac{E}{c^2} = \frac{q\varphi}{c^2} \quad (110)$$

Strangely the electromagnetic wave is moving at the speed of light in everywhere direction from the surface of the electron, this might seem to violate causality, after all it's saying the electron is moving both at the speed of light and the classical velocity, but there are a couple of remedies, firstly the spin takes place in $\mathbb{R}^{1,3}$ while the movement of the charge takes place in \mathbb{R}^3 , secondly, this doesn't violate conservation of energy because of the Poynting vector,

$$\mathbf{S} = \frac{1}{\mu_0} \mathbf{E} \times \mathbf{B} \quad (111)$$

Which gives the flow of energy from Maxwell's equations, if we sum over the total surface of the sphere in $\mathbb{R}^{1,3}$ then the total flow of energy is zero, which means that all the electromagnetic waves cancel each other out leaving a zero net field. So there is no paradox, and modelling the electron as a spinning electromagnetic wave can allow two different velocities, the real problem here is visualising a spinning four-component electromagnetic wave.

We can generalise this spinning electromagnetic wave equation as

$$\square^2 A_\mu^{int} = -\frac{4\pi}{c} j_\mu^{int} \quad (112)$$

Comparing the above derivation for a matter wave to the equation for a photon, we note as Griffiths writes:

“In quantum electrodynamics the A^μ becomes the wave function of the photon. The free photon satisfies this equation

$$\square^2 A^\mu = \frac{4\pi}{c} J^\mu \quad (113)$$

[note the sign in the current is arbitrary, so equally we can write]

$$\square^2 A^\mu = -\frac{4\pi}{c} J^\mu \quad (114)$$

but for $J^\mu = 0$

$$\square^2 A^\mu = 0 \quad (3.10)$$

... which we recognise in this context as the Klein-Gordon equation for a massless particle.” - [Griffiths 1987 p227],

and here we see an electromagnetic wave equation can indeed be written for matter as well as for light. This model strongly suggests that just like Maxwell’s use of Ampere’s Law in his derivation of light as an electromagnetic wave equation with a velocity for light

$$\nabla \times \mathbf{E} = -\frac{1}{c} \frac{\partial \mathbf{B}}{\partial t} \quad (115)$$

We, in this model, require

$$\nabla \cdot \mathbf{A}_{\text{int}} = -\frac{1}{c} \frac{\partial \varphi_{\text{ext}}}{\partial t} \quad (116)$$

to balance Maxwell’s equations.

Now can we put any numbers on this model?

Wolfgang Pauli pointed out that for a point particle when using a *solid moment of inertia* for the electron and equating to the Bohr magneton \hbar results in a rotation *a thousand times faster than the speed of light*, which is clearly untenable, in other words *we can’t have a solid electron*.

On the other hand if the electron is an electromagnetic wave travelling on the surface of a shell at the speed of light, then we can calculate the radius of the electron from a *spinning thin shell* with a moment of inertia I_e given by

$$I_e = \frac{2}{3} m_e r_e^2 \quad (117)$$

with angular velocity ω to give the angular momentum by equating to the Bohr magneton \hbar

$$I_e \omega = \frac{2}{3} m_e r_e^2 \omega = \hbar \quad (118)$$

However, two orthogonal components of angular momentum (for example L_x and L_y) are complementary and cannot be simultaneously known or measured, except in special cases such as

$$L_x = L_y = L_z = 0 \quad (119)$$

Therefore we restrict ourselves to just one of the spatial axes X, Y, Z to determine the angular momentum and take just 1/3 of the total angular momentum

$$I_e \omega = \frac{2}{3} m_e r_e^2 \omega = \frac{\hbar}{3} \quad (120)$$

writing $\omega = v_e / r_e$

$$\frac{2}{3} m_e r_e^2 \frac{v_e}{r_e} = \frac{\hbar}{3} \quad (121)$$

rearranging

$$r_e = \frac{1}{2} \frac{\hbar}{m_e v_e} \quad (122)$$

This, however, is the rotation of the electron four-vector in $\mathbb{R}^{1,3}$, since the electromagnetic wave is moving at the speed of light c , substitute $v_e = c$, and noting the reduced Compton wavelength is λ

$$\lambda = \frac{\hbar}{m_e c} \quad (123)$$

yielding the simple result that radius of the electron is half its Compton wavelength

$$r_e = \frac{1}{2} \lambda \quad (124)$$

and therefore the *diameter of the electron d_e is identical to the Compton wavelength,*

$$d_e = \lambda = 3.86159 * 10^{-13} \text{ (meters)} \quad (125)$$

Now we would expect this result as the reduced Compton wavelength appears in both the Klein–Gordon equation and the Dirac equation, so necessarily any model of the electron should carry with it the reduced Compton wavelength as a defining characteristic.

We can also note the electron amplitude Λ appears to given by the projected A_μ vectors in \mathbb{R}^3 or $\Lambda = r_e$, suggesting means the electron moves as a pure sine wave-form, and now we can give a 2D projected picture of the electromagnetic matter wave as:

(fig. 4)

You can clearly see in the diagram the electron radius is $\frac{1}{2}$ the length of the wavelength λ ; and you can also see the advanced and retarded potential originate on the bounding edges of the electron along the axis of time. You won't see the wavefunction as a Gaussian wave packet because the wave-form is along the entire axis of time, if we try to localise this to a point in time then, yes, this would be a Gaussian wave packet.

This exact result for the radius, amplitude and wavelength of an electron from the Compton wavelength is almost a *quod erat demonstrandum* of the electromagnetic wave model. It says the spin, radius, amplitude and wavelength of the electron are intrinsically coupled to the four-vector potential, it says that elementary particles are both — particles in \mathbb{R}^3 — and — waves in $\mathbb{R}^{1,3}$ —, and that the wave—particle duality is a genuine physical phenomena.

It should be a beautiful result, *however*, there is a serious problem with the model because it doesn't agree with the experimental result as put forward by the Nobel prize winning researcher Hans Georg Dehmelt. Dehmelt

suggested the electron radius must be less than 10^{-22} (meters) by arguing that the electron radius was determined by an ‘*internal structure*’ for the electron, and from this internal structure the gyromagnetic ratio (or the ratio of its magnetic moment to its angular momentum) must determine the electron radius

$$|g - g_{dirac}| = \frac{r_e}{\lambda} \quad (126)$$

where $g_{dirac} = 2$ is the gyromagnetic factor, or

$$|g - 2| = \frac{r_e}{\lambda} \quad (127)$$

“*It appears that this combination of current data is not in harmony with electron structure models assuming special symmetries that predict the quadratic relation $|g - 2| = (\frac{r_e}{\lambda})^2$ shown by the dashed line(sic). This favours the linear relation used in the above extrapolation of R for the electron. Thus, the electron may have size and structure!*”⁴

Dehmelt based his model on resonances in the Penning trap for multi energy level atoms (which certainly have internal structure); as well as for protons (and we now know protons have an internal structure); and for the hypothetical ‘*metastable pseudo-atom geonium*’ particle, all by coupling the angular momentum of the electron to its magnetic moment.

But I’m going to argue the electron has *no* ‘*internal structure*’, rather what we consider the structure is determined by the extrinsic potentials not within the intrinsic potential of electron itself, and as a result there is also no self-interaction, I’m suggesting the magnetic moment appears in the \mathbb{R}^3 frame

4 “*Experiments with an isolated subatomic particle at rest*” Hans G. Dehmelt Nobel Lecture, December 8, 1989.

of reference while the angular momentum is in the $\mathbb{R}^{1,3}$ frame of reference so they don't couple together. The angular momentum appears on transforming from $\mathbb{R}^{1,3}$ to \mathbb{R}^3 they are not simultaneously in the same frame of reference. I think this is an explicit reference to Ohanian's comment, "... *that neither the spin nor the magnetic moment are "internal"—they are not associated with the internal structure of the electron, but rather with the structure of its wave field.*"

This implies Dehmelt's model is at fault and he was in fact measuring something that could not be measured, in fact, by Dehmelt's own words he said the electron radius must be less than 10^{-22} (meters) but he didn't actually measure the radius only that in his model it has an upper bound of 10^{-22} (meters); because of this I'm suggesting we can indeed use the reduced Compton wavelength as the basis for the electron radius,

$$r_e = \frac{\lambda}{2} = 1.9308 * 10^{-14}(\text{meters}) \quad (128)$$

In other words, the electron radius of this model exactly corresponds to the classical electron radius, and this whole process is very similar to Maxwell determining the velocity of his electromagnetic wave exactly corresponding to the measured of light, so surely this really is a beautiful result.

–As an aside, it is interesting to reverse this whole process by starting from the Compton wavelength,

$$\lambda = \frac{h}{m_e c} \quad (129)$$

equating the radius

$$r_e = \frac{1}{2} \frac{\hbar}{m_e v_e} \quad (130)$$

substituting $\omega = v_e/r_e$

$$\frac{2}{3} m_e r_e^2 \frac{v_e}{r_e} = \frac{\hbar}{3} \quad (131)$$

and noting the electron spin

$$I_e = \frac{2}{3} m_e r_e^2 \quad (132)$$

and by equating the angular momentum to the Bohr magneton \hbar

$$I_e \omega = \frac{2}{3} m_e r_e^2 \omega = \hbar \quad (133)$$

We have shown the intrinsic electron spin is equal to Planck's constant, this may seem a bit of a given, but the important point to note is that this method only works for a thin electric shell for a massive particle not for a solid or point particle, in other words Spin is a necessary consequence of this shell model.

§5 Electromagnetic Mass

Next let's consider what electromagnetic mass might be for a spinning

electromagnetic wave.

J.J. Thomson [Thomson 1881], Oliver Heaviside [Heaviside 1889], George Searle [Searle 1897], Wilhelm Wien [Wien 1900], Max Abraham [Abraham 1902], Hendrik Lorentz [Lorentz (1892,1904)], Henri Poincaré [Poincaré 1905] et al, developed the charged spherical shell model for the electron, and concluded the electromagnetic-mass relation for a static charge with electrostatic mass $m_{e.s.}$ and electrostatic energy $E_{e.s}$

$$m_{e.s.} = \frac{E_{e.s.}}{c^2} \quad (134)$$

Yet this contradicted when the mass is derived from the Lorentz-Abraham equations for electromagnetic mass $m_{e.m.}$ and electromagnetic energy $E_{e.m.}$ yielding

$$m_{e.m.} = \frac{4}{3} \frac{E_{e.m.}}{c^2} \quad (135)$$

Clearly the 4/3 factor was a problem, to solve this Poincaré [1905] suggested the addition of internal stresses $E_{Poincaré}$ to give an extra 1/3 electromagnetic term.

$$\frac{E_{total}}{c^2} = \frac{E_{e.s.}}{c^2} + \frac{1}{3} \frac{E_{Poincaré}}{c^2} = \frac{4}{3} \frac{E_{e.m.}}{c^2} = \frac{4}{3} m_{e.s.} = m_{e.m.} \quad (136)$$

I'm going to suggest these Poincaré stresses can be achieved by considering that a spinning electron also carries rotational field energy along with its electrical field energy and the source of this rotational energy lies in the magnetic vector potential. To demonstrate this, first write the magnetic vector

potential in terms of the Wheeler-Feynman model, where in \mathbb{R}^3 the φ_{ext} is the intrinsic electric potential and \mathbf{A}_{int} is the intrinsic magnetic vector potential

$$\begin{aligned}
 -\frac{1}{c} \frac{d\varphi_{\mu}^{tot}}{dt} &= -\sum \frac{1}{2c} \left(\frac{\partial\varphi_{ret}}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial\varphi_{adv}}{\partial t} \right) - \sum \frac{1}{2c} \left(\frac{\partial\varphi_{ret}}{\partial t} - \frac{\partial\varphi_{adv}}{\partial t} \right) \\
 &= \nabla \cdot \mathbf{A}_{int}
 \end{aligned}
 \tag{137}$$

again the \mathbf{A}_{int} and φ_{ext} can be used to write the action S of the wave function

$$S = q \int A_{\mu} dx^{\mu} = q \int \varphi_{ext} dt + q \int \mathbf{A}_{int} d\mathbf{x}
 \tag{138}$$

This allows us to express the total action in \mathbb{R}^3 in terms of energy and angular momentum

$$S = \int E dt + \int \mathbf{p} \cdot d\mathbf{x}
 \tag{139}$$

The first term can be used to derive the electrical field energy that gives rise to the $E_{electrostatic}$ field energy which in turn yields the electrostatic mass. The second term can be used to derive the rotational field energy from the angular momentum, this requires determining momentum from a mechanism involving $q\mathbf{A}$. If we now equate the mechanical angular momentum to the intrinsic electromagnetic spin we get,

$$I\omega = q \int_a^{\infty} \mathbf{A}_{int} \cdot d\mathbf{x}
 \tag{140}$$

This is the *important step*, for as the vector potential varies so does the angular momentum, by applying this to the momentum of inertia for a spherical

shell with radius a (which as pointed out above we can do for this model)

$$I_{sphere} = \frac{2}{3}ma^2 \quad (141)$$

we arrive at the rotational kinetic energy

$$E_{rotational} \equiv E_{magnetic} \quad (142)$$

Now we can substitute this result in place of the Poincaré stresses to obtain a balanced mass equation and show the masses are entirely electromagnetic in origin (at least for charged leptons),

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{E_{total}}{c^2} &= (E_{electric} + \frac{1}{3}E_{magnetic})/c^2 \\ &= (E_{electrostatic} + \frac{1}{3}E_{Poincaré})/c^2 \\ &= \frac{4}{3}(E_{electromagnetic})/c^2 \\ &= m_{electromagnetic} \end{aligned} \quad (143)$$

For now we are lead to the conclusion that electromagnetic mass and spin are connected, and state as a general rule:

mass is a form of electromagnetism

§6 Pictures

So what does all this look like? It is easier to visualise as the intersection

of two three-dimensional potentials where the two-dimensional disc is equivalent to the three-dimensional intrinsic potential, but if we note that the intersection of two four-dimensional spheres is a three-dimensional sphere with the resultant potential pointing radially away from the centre of the 3-sphere, we can get a better understanding of the underlying dynamics.

In figure (5) it helps to understand that while each of these intersections is a 90° in $\mathbb{R}^{1,3}$, they are also 45° in \mathbb{R}^3 , and they also appear as interior angles that range from $\pi/2$ to $-\pi/2$ in \mathbb{R}^2 . Importantly, none of the resultant intrinsic potentials are within the radius of the particle, requiring the particle be hollow and that the charge is entirely on the surface of the particle.

Also the angle between $A(\varphi_{ext}, 0)$ and the motion of the particle is at 45° , which shouldn't be the case in $\mathbb{R}^{1,3}$ as each of the axis are at 90° to each other, however, on transforming into \mathbb{R}^3 the light cone is rotated at 45° to the spatial coördinates, this is simply a fact of four dimensional geometry. On the other hand for any other angles the potentials are not in phase, for *that would violate conservation of energy, necessarily it must be 45°* . (fig. 5)

You will also note the resultant sum is not in the frame of reference of either the advanced or retarded potentials, rather it is a loci midway between the advanced and retarded frames, so a better choice of language would be to distinguish the frames into past, present and future frames of reference. I think this was a problem with the Wheeler-Feynman formulation where it appeared

the retarded field *is* the resultant field, while for this model the magnitude of the resultant potential is equal to the magnitudes of either advanced or retarded potentials, the result in this model is a sum of those frames of reference, which is a much more reasonable idea (at least in flat space).

For illustrative purposes it's easy enough to superimpose a wavelength upon the diagram for a spherical charged shell; momentum moving along the world line; a wavelength beginning and ending on the advanced and retarded sources; and the amplitude is drawn as the radius of the sphere, but here we have superimposed $\mathbb{R}^{1,3}$ vectors on a \mathbb{R}^2 space so it doesn't quite look right. (fig. 6)

If we include the four-vector potentials we get a much more complicated diagram, where the interior disk is the electron and the exterior disks are the potentials, but this comes from layering the electron in \mathbb{R}^3 over the potentials in $\mathbb{R}^{1,3}$ so it can be ambiguous where and what everything is supposed to be, although you can clearly see the A_μ^{ret} , A_μ^{int} and A_μ^{adv} are all in phase, also while the potentials have a wavelength in $\mathbb{R}^{1,3}$ equal to twice the wavelength in \mathbb{R}^3 we

can only measure the wavelength of the electron in \mathbb{R}^3 so we can ignore problem. Essentially these are two separate entities that are coupled through Maxwell's equations and evolve over time as both an electron and a wavefunction:

(fig. 7)

§7 Experiment

Finally, this model is compatible with the experimental evidence found for electromagnetic longitudinal scalar waves as shown by C. Monstein and J.P. Wesley, ‘*Observation of Scalar Longitudinal Electrodynamical Waves,*’ Europhysics Letters 59, no. 4 (2002): 514-520, who using a set up that was little more than a spherical radiator and spherical receiver with metal rods piercing a

wooden board between the spheres they were able to block the longitudinal waves. Where the longitudinal component of an oscillating electric field was effectively “*blocked when the polarising rods were parallel to the direction of propagation, and practically unaffected when it was perpendicular.*”

This suggests that if test electrons were projected along the longitudinal axis of such a longitudinal scalar wave they would deviate in comparison to electrons projected in the transverse axis, in a manner similar to the Stern–Gerlach experiment. In other words, given the simplicity of the Monstein and Wesley experiment this model of an electron moving as a longitudinal wave can be easily tested.

Summary

This model starts from the Wheeler-Feynman summation and generalizes it to the four-vector potential and the action principle to derive an electromagnetic wave equation that carries charge, mass and spin much like an electron or quark. Just like Maxwell’s derivation of the electromagnetic equation for light that requires the addition a displacement current as a correction to Ampère’s Circuital Law to balance Maxwell’s equations, this model also must include a novel magnetic vector potential to also satisfy Maxwell’s equations, and this is the key point the model works by balancing Maxwell’s electromagnetic equations.

Thus by applying the Wheeler-Feynman time-symmetric theory to the four-vector potential there appears in the inertial frame of the observed particle a four dimensional inhomogeneous electromagnetic wave function in $\mathbb{R}^{1,3}$ space which has a radius, mass, charge and most importantly a spin with a double

rotation in \mathbb{R}^3 space. What stands out is the velocity of the derived particle exactly matches the classical velocity of the particle, the diameter of the particle is the exact solution for the reduced Compton wavelength λ , and the rate of spin of the particle exactly matches the rate of the known quantum spin (360° to 720°). So I'm going to suggest this is a viable model for the electron as an electromagnetic wave with charge e , wavelength λ , spin \hbar and velocity \mathbf{v} in the same manner as Maxwell modelled the motion of light as an electromagnetic wave with velocity c and wavelength λ .

Indeed this method of generating a spinning, charged electromagnetic wave is so very similar to Maxwell's original solution for the electromagnetic wave equation in his 1865 paper:

A Dynamical Theory of the Electromagnetic Field

that to acknowledge this correspondence I have named this paper:

A Dynamical Theory of the Electromagnetic Potential

In a real sense this *is* a generalisation of Maxwell's method seeking to balance Maxwell's equations to generate an electromagnetic wave, and while one balances time varying fields and the other balances time varying potentials, and while they are separated over 150 years in time — they are essentially the same model.

REFERENCES

Maxwell, James Clerk., “A Dynamical Theory of the Electromagnetic Field”.
Philosophical Transactions of the Royal Society of London. 155: 459–512.
(Paper read at a meeting of the Royal Society on 8 December 1864).

Wheeler, J.A.; Feynman, R.P., “Interaction with the Absorber as the Mechanism
of Radiation”, *Reviews of Modern Physics*. 17 (2-3): 157-181, (April 1945).

Wheeler, J. A.; Feynman, R. P., “Classical Electrodynamics in Terms of Direct
Interparticle Action”, *Reviews of Modern Physics*. 21 (3): 425-433. (July 1949).

Griffiths, D.J., *Introduction to Elementary Particles* (2nd ed.). John Wiley &
Sons. (2008).

Griffiths, D.J., *Introduction to Electrodynamics* (4th ed.). Cambridge University
Press. (2017).

Monstein, C. and Wesley, J. P., “Observation of scalar longitudinal
electrodynamic waves”, *Europhys. Lett.*, 59 (4), pp. 514–520 (2002).